

THE INFLUENCE OF COLOR IN FRAGRANCE PERCEPTION

DESIGNING PACKAGINGS FOR PERFUMES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a discussion about the importance of the use of colors in a packaging design for perfumes. Facing the potentiality of such visual stimuli in optimizing the user experience in the moment of choosing and buying. In this paper we point out the particularities of a packaging design for a product such as perfume. We discuss the use of verbal metaphor to describe fragrances, and we also discuss the possibility of associating smells and colors through such metaphors. Materials, methods, and the results of a survey with Brazilian consumers are presented here. The results were compared with the fragrance market practices, and lead us to conclude that certain colors better reflect the message of a fragrance. We argue, therefore, that once using the appropriate colors in packaging design, the communication can be enhanced, and the perception of the quality of a perfume can be anticipated even before it is smelt.

KEYWORDS: *packaging design, color, perfume, consumer perception, Brazil.*

INTRODUCTION

Packaging plays an important role for the perfumery industry and market. The visual communication applied to a packaging design may increase its influence over the consumer. We argue that, among other factors, the color of packaging has influence over fragrance perception. Before discussing this factor, we will conduct a brief introduction about the particularities of designing packaging for perfumes.

Packaging is as important as the perfume it contains. Unlike other kinds of packaging, which in their origin were more concerned with the strength and capacity of storage, the packaging used to protect and store the perfumes have been treated for centuries with the care given to an object of art. By analyzing the perfumery history, we can see that the perfume was for many years exclusive to the nobility (Silva, 2012). As a luxury item, the packaging of perfumes also carried the trappings of an object worthy of the nobility. The finest materials and techniques were used, varying according to the historical moment of each culture. Today, perfume is available to the masses. In spite of this, the primacy of beauty still remains in the design for perfume packaging. Throughout perfume's trajectory in society, many changes have occurred in the social, economic, political, technological, and environmental

spheres. Two events, though, have affected the paradigms of packaging design: the industrial revolution and the system of sales in large retail.

With the advent of industrialization, coupled with mass consumption of perfumes, manufacturers were faced with the possibility of producing packaging in a fast and economical way so as to meet the growing market. For many years, extraordinary artisans were in charge of packaging design for perfumes (Mariacher, 1992). However, with industrialization, the packaging production passes into the hands of a large team. Engineers, technicians, machine operators, marketing professionals, and designers all play a role in this chain of production. The implementation of self-service in the mid-twentieth century (Camargo & Negrão, 2008) is a second milestone in the production of packaging. The emergence of retail trade and supermarkets modifies the dynamics of sales. No more are those sellers behind the counter, listening and answering every consumer's doubts and appeals. Packaging will be responsible for providing the necessary information concerning technical, regulatory, and commercial issues. It should also be attractive and compelling; it needs to be self salable. As packaging specialists usually say, packaging is now playing the role of a 'silent salesman' (Pilditch, 1961). Such changes in the production and in the system of

sales have been demanding new skills and knowledge. The designer should comprehend the limitations of industrial production so as to take advantage of it. In this way they can design packaging, which will make a difference to both the company and the consumer.

Among the different approaches that can be woven around a packaging design, we chose to analyze, in this paper, the influence of visual communication elements in the packaging for perfumes; and, more specifically, the usage of colors for communicating the characteristics of each one of the fragrances. In a project of this nature, where what has been selling is the fragrance with its promises of welfare, seduction, and freshness (Ashcar, 2011), packaging must communicate such attributes. We therefore believe that the visual elements such as shape, texture, and color must be consistent with the stimuli that the fragrance will supposedly trigger in the consumer. Given the power of colors to affect people, proven by its extensive use in communication, we decided to focus this investigation on them. Could colors represent the smells?

Scientists have proven that to visually identify a smell is not an easy task, because olfactory perceptions vary from individual to individual (Wolfe et al., 2012). Nevertheless, research in the field of neuroscience in different countries has shown positive results that point to a cross-modal association among the different senses. Encouraged by this, we decided to investigate possible associations between colors and smells in the Brazilian market. As such, this study aims to present results and reflections about the perception of a group of consumers. Despite perceptions being particular to each individual, there is indeed a trend of certain associations between colors and smells.

THE OLFATORY MESSAGE TRANSLATED INTO VISUAL AND VERBAL LANGUAGE

Communication in the world has been long dominated by verbal language, that is, by speech. Certainly, our body language is the most immediate way to express feelings. It is linked to instincts and involuntary responses in our body. However, expressing feelings is different from communicating feelings. When the intention is to share with our peers what we are feeling, we frequently use words to do it. In what concerns smells, we can react to an odor only by facial expression. But to share this feeling with someone else requires a little more information. Considering that humans have difficulty in verbalizing a smell and that the ability to discriminate between them varies according to a range of facts such as gender, age, and experience (Wolfe et al., 2012), to communicate an olfactory perception is not an easy task. 'When one tries to describe the smell elicited by a rose, for example, it will require multiple words, representing feelings, emotions, or memories of the individual' (Teixeira et al., 2013, p.97). Because of this, we can have different interpretations about the same smells. Indeed, the complexity of the olfactory system creates difficulty to have a unique definition for each odor. The

perfumery industry, though, has invested in building a vocabulary to facilitate identification and discrimination of odors (Teixeira et al., 2013; Zarzo & Stanton, 2009; Donna, 2009).

Given the extensive range of ingredients available in the world of perfumery, it is a common market practice to classify fragrances in olfactory families. This classification can vary from company to company, although highly trained specialists have done it. Despite being largely classified by empirical methods, recently, perfumes can be classified by technological processes such as the 'Perfumery Radar methodology', which consists of a software tool developed by a group of engineers with the purpose of 'reducing the arbitrariness to the empirical classification' (Teixeira et al., 2013, p.113). For this research, however, we have opted for the classification presented by the digital magazine Osmoz (Table one), elaborated by the Firmenich fragrance company. Even though it is an empirical classification, it is a recognized reference in the perfumery market. Moreover, Osmoz presents an approach that comes from meeting with the goal of this research. The magazine presents a definition for each one of the olfactory families (Table 1). In doing so, the consumer can have an idea of the feelings each family may elicit.

Just as people use words to describe smells, we know that in the field of visual language qualities are also assigned to colors. In the case of colors, we have the universal classification of warm and cold colors, which is a reflection of people's experience in daily life. The fire, which makes us feel warm, usually varies from yellow to red (warm colors). The ice, which makes us feel cold, is the water in a solid stage. The water in its turn is seen as blue (cold color) when in a higher concentration. However we have been giving meanings to the colors which are much more abstract than this. Studies of Goethe (2013), Kandinsky (2000), and Farina (1986) show an attempt at translating colors into sensations; that is, an attempt to describe the psychological effects of colors on people.

Given the predominance of the verbal language in our societies, we can infer that the use of verbal metaphors is a natural attitude when people want to express feelings. If the words are capable of translating odors and visual stimuli, it means that in some way we can connect these feelings to words. Especially if we assume that all the senses are connected. In other words, if we consider that there are not 'departmentalized senses, but synesthesias as interrelationship of all the senses' (Plaza, 1987, p.46). From that thought, we decided to conduct consumer research using verbal language as a connection to the possible association between colors and smells.

COULD THE COLORS REPRESENT THE SMELLS?

It is common sense that colors are an important element in communicating emotions. Miguel Teixeira and his colleagues (Teixeira et al., 2013, p.99) assume that the look of a perfume (including its colors) greatly influences its judgment. They argue that the process of fragrance perception is hierarchical (Figure 1). It is initially influenced by culture, memories, and

OLFACTORY FAMILIES	DEFINITIONS/ ATTRIBUTES
Oriental (Men)	Refreshed by aromatic or citrus facets, oriental compositions draw their richness and sophistication from precious substances such as amber, resin, tobacco, spices, exotic woods, and animal notes.
Oriental (Women)	Oriental —also known as 'amber' fragrances — stand out because of their unique blend of warmth and sensuality. They draw their richness from heady substances like musk, vanilla, and precious woods that are often associated with exotic floral and spicy scents.
Citrus(Men)	This family includes all perfumes mainly composed of citrus notes such as bergamot, lemon, orange, tangerine, and grapefruit. These fragrances are characterized by their freshness and lightness. The first 'Eaux de Cologne' belongs to this category. The masculine character comes from the frequently strong presence of aromatic and spicy notes.
Citrus(Women)	Each perfume in this family is primarily composed of citrus scents such as bergamot, lemon, orange, tangerine, and grapefruit, to which other orange-tree elements (orange blossoms, petit grain, or neroli oil) have been added. Floral or even chypre accords are sometimes present as well. These perfumes are characterized by their freshness and lightness including the first 'Eaux de Cologne'.
Woody	These perfumes, with their woody middle note, are warm and opulent when based on sandalwood or patchouli. Cedar and vetiver make them dryer. These warm, dry, and elegant masculine accords often contain a dash of citrus or aromatic notes.
Floral	This family is composed of a large variety of creations ranging from sumptuous bouquet arrangements to 'soli flora' compositions. Perfumers can let their creativity run wild, enriching florals with green, aldehydic, fruity, or spicy hints. With its natural scent, the floral note is one of the most widely used in women's perfumes.
Aromatic	Aromatic notes are mainly composed of sage, rosemary, thyme, and lavender usually complemented with citrus and spicy notes. These compositions' manly character makes them an all-time favorite in men's perfumery.
Chypre	Chypre by Coty enjoyed such success in 1917 that 'chypre' is now a generic name for a whole category of timeless, classic perfumes. The compositions are based on oak moss, ciste-labdanum, patchouli and bergamot accords. The richness of chypre notes mixes wonderfully with fruity or floral notes. This family is made up of distinguished, instantly recognizable fragrances.

Table 1. Characteristics of some olfactory families. Source: Osmoz magazine. (2013).

Figure 1. The pyramid of scent perception based on Teixeira et al. (2013, p.99).

Figure 2. Fragrance wheel by Michael Edwards, from *Fragrances of the World* website.

past experiences. Then, in a second stage, we have the influence of the other sensory stimuli such as sight, taste, hearing, and touch. Based on this, we can infer that colors can represent smells.

Besides this, we could observe, by analyzing the perfumery segment, the trend of using colors so as representing smells. The fragrance wheel created by the fragrance expert Michael Edwards (Figure 2) is an example of this. In a quick search on the Internet we can find lots of attempts of fragrance classification by a colorful wheel. Moreover, some research has been undertaken both in the cosmetics segment (Kim, 2009; Milotic, 2006) and in the drinks (Gilbert et al., 1996; Moran, 2011; Morrot et al., 2001) with the objective of identifying such associations. Despite the peculiarities of olfactory perception (factors such as age and sex have influence over it) the results show that the colors can influence odors. Based on this, we decided to investigate the Brazilian market by opposing consumer opinion to market practice.

Materials and methods

We elaborated an online survey in order to investigate how consumers react to the names of olfactory families and also the characteristics attributed to them. Through this approach we aim to investigate how familiar with the perfumery vocabulary the consumers were. Moreover, we aim to identify if the associations which consumers make between color and smells are similar to those we can find in the market. The online survey was elaborated in Google Drive tool and it was distributed through the social network of the authors, mostly composed of designers and design students. However, the professional occupation was not an issue of selection. Respondents were encouraged to spread the survey to their re-

spective social networks. Only personal information, such as age, gender, and city of residence were collected. In a period of one month (from 11/17/2013 to 12/13/2013), we obtained a total of 159 respondents (106 women and 53 men). The majority of respondents (80%) were under 35, and over 90% were residents from the Southeast region.

Respondents were not asked about their habits of consumption of perfumes. They were only asked to freely associate words (olfactory family names and their attributes) to one or more colors. We opted to use a qualitative approach and employed open-ended questions in order to avoid influence over the respondents. For this survey we selected the most known families of fragrances in the Brazilian market: citrus, floral, woody, and oriental. For each one of these families, we chose two words that according to the perfumery literature better represent the emotion elicited by them (see Table 1). For Citrus we have the qualities of *freshness and lightness*. Based on the floral olfactory family speech we could infer the qualities of *romantic and feminine*. With regard to the woody family we selected the qualities *warm and elegant*. Finally for the oriental family we selected the qualities of *sophistication (richness) and sensuality*. It is important to highlight that respondents were not informed that those qualities had a connection with the olfactory families presented. Moreover, the four qualities were presented in a different order to the olfactory families.

Two questions were posed to the consumers. Each one of them was divided into four sub questions (four attributes and four olfactory families). The first question posed was 'What color or colors do you associate with perfumes which have the following characteristics?'. This question was followed by an example: 'Blue, light blue, silver, gold, dark green... You can inform the color and the tone that you feel is most appropriate'. Then the four sub questions were presented:¹ (1) *Freshness and lightness*, (2) *Sophistication and sensuality*, (3) *Warm and elegant*, (4) *Romantic and feminine*. The second question presented was 'What color or colors do you associate with perfumes which belong to the following olfactory families?'. The same example given in the first question was given in this second one. The sub questions presented were: (1) *Citrus Perfume*, (2) *Woody Perfume*, (3) *Floral Perfume*, (4) *Oriental Perfume*. In doing so, our aim was to identify if the colors mentioned for each olfactory family would coincide with those colors indicated for the characteristics associated to each one of these families. That is, if the colors displayed for citrus perfume were similar to the colors indicated for the attributes of *freshness and lightness*.

Results

The table bellow summarizes the results obtained from the research. As mentioned before, consumers were free to give the answers to the questions. As a result of this, we got a va-

¹ In the original language (Portuguese) the qualities presented were: (1) *Frescor e Leveza*, (2) *Sofisticação e Sensualidade*, (3) *Quente e Elegante*, (4) *Romântico e feminino*.

	CITRUS	FRESHNESS AND LIGHTNESS
TOTAL OF MENTIONED COLORS	208 (100%)	223 (100%)
1st most mentioned color	Green - 88 (42%)	Green - 81 (36.3%)
2nd most mentioned color	Yellow - 50 (24%)	Blue - 75 (33.6%)
3rd most mentioned color	Orange - 48 (23%)	Lilac - 12 (5.4%) Yellow - 12 (5.4%)
	Woody	Warm and elegant
Total of mentioned colors	190 (100%)	217 (100%)
1st most mentioned color	Brown - 98 (51.6%)	Red - 83 (38.2%)
2nd most mentioned color	Yellow - 16 (8.4%)	Orange - 29 (13.4%)
3rd most mentioned color	Green - 13 (6.8%)	Golden - 24 (11%)
	Floral	Romantic and feminine
Total of mentioned colors	226 (100%)	219 (100%)
1st most mentioned color	Pink - 103 (45.6%)	Pink - 128 (58.4%)
2nd most mentioned color	Purple/ lilac - 35 (15.5%)	Purple/ lilac - 24 (10.9%)
3rd most mentioned color	Yellow - 26 (11.5%)	Red - 17 (7.8%)
	Oriental	Sophistication and sensuality
Total of mentioned colors	198 (100%)	229 (100%)
1st most mentioned color	Red - 63 (31.8%)	Red - 69 (30%)
2nd most mentioned color	Yellow - 21 (10.6%)	Golden - 38 (16.6%)
3rd most mentioned color	White - 18 (9%)	Purple/ lilac - 31 (13.5%)

Table 2. Results of consumer research. Source: Created by the authors.

riety of nomenclatures. Light green, dark green, royal blue, bright red, sunset red, ice, amber, crystal white, old rose, burned rose, tropical colors: just to give some examples. We considered, though, in a single group the different variations of tones from light to dark from the same hue. That is, when we mention yellow we refer to the different yellows informed by the consumers.

Analyzing the results shown in Table 2, and comparing it with the fragrance wheel (Figure 3), we can identify correlations between consumers' opinions and the colors chosen by Michael Edwards to represent such fragrances. The citrus family is represented in the fragrance wheel by the color yellow, the second most mentioned by the respondents. For the floral family, the fragrance wheel presents three variations. Selecting only the floral and soft floral (excluding floral oriental because it merges floral with another family, the oriental) we can see that the pink and red colors are used, as mentioned by the respondents. With regard to the woody family, the wheel presents the use of yellowish brown and tones of green, again according to the responses obtained in the survey. Finally, in the oriental family we have the use of a rosy red tone. From this first analysis we can infer that, even though the perceptions vary from person to person, some colors can be associated with the smells. In order to investigate the correspondences between colors and smells, we proceed to the analysis comparing the associations revealed in the survey answers (characteristics and olfactory families) with the market practices. For this purpose we selected some packag-

Figure 3. Citrus, floral, woody, oriental: the colors of the families according to Michael Edwards.

ing of Brazilian perfumes, which are classified in the citrus, floral, woody, and oriental families.

Looking at the table with the results it is interesting to observe the influence of raw material on the association of col-

ors and smells. In the citrus family, the three most mentioned colors are the same we can find in the fruits used as raw material for this kind of fragrance, such as lemon, orange, bergamot, and mandarine. Besides that, over 60% of the listed colors were green and yellow as seen in the packaging of perfumes from the *Natura* company for citrus fragrances (Figure 4). It is worth highlighting that the colors yellow and green are also mentioned for the attributes used for citrus fragrances. The color blue, the second most mentioned as the color for the attributes of freshness and lightness, almost had the same amount of indications as the color green. Blue is a color universally used to represent the cold. In addition to this, we can notice that *Natura* also uses the color blue for a citrus fragrance. Moreover, we argue that the colors presented in open-air natural spaces may influence the perception of freshness: the colors of forest (green) and of the ocean (blue), the grass (green), and the sky (blue).

As for the floral family, the most mentioned colors were pink and purple/lilac, totaling more than 60%, probably because these colors are commonly found in flowers. In addition to this, it is very common to find perfumes from floral olfactory families using these kinds of colors. If we take a look at some of the packaging of *Natura's* perfumes, we can confirm this tendency (Figure 5). When consumers were asked to indicate

colors related to the attributes of their family (*romantic and feminine*), again they mentioned pink and purple/lilac. The color red was also mentioned. Once again we can notice a connection here between scents, words, and colors. Because flowers and romanticism are connected in the collective imaginary of people's daily life, the results could not be different. In a quick search on the Internet we can find flowers as a symbolism of women and romance. Furthermore, 'the floral note is one of the most widely used in women's perfumes' (see Table 1).

With regard to the woody olfactory family, brown and its variations were mentioned in more than 50% of responses. Brown is the color of the wood, so that was a natural association to be made. We believe that, because they were not submitted to olfactory stimulus, the consumers made a connection with what they consider as raw material for the fragrances of the woody family; that is, the tree. Consequently they also mentioned other colors related to trees: yellow and green (leaves and twigs). As for the colors mentioned to the attributes of warm and elegant, even though they were not the same ones indicated to the woody family, we can established a kind of connection among the responses. The color brown can easily vary to tones of yellow, oranges and reds. In this sense, all the responses have a connection. Brown, yellow, orange,

Figure 4. Citrus fragrances from the *Natura* company.

Figure 5. Floral fragrances from the *Natura* company

Figure 6. Woody fragrances from the *Natura* company

Figure 7. Oriental fragrances from the *O Boticário* company

red: they are all warm colors. Analyzing the packaging of perfumes of the *Natura* company, we can see the use of the colors mentioned by the respondents (Figure 6).

Finally, it was in the oriental family that we could observe more variation in the results. We did not have a strong indication for just one or two colors. If we consider the most mentioned color, the oriental family was the one that had less votes, 31.8% for the color red. For citrus we have the first mentioned color (green) concentrating 42% of the votes. In the floral, we have 45.6% concentrated in the color pink. In the woody family, we have 51.6% concentrated in the color brown. In spite of this, and taking account the three most mentioned colors, there is a predominance of warm colors. This has everything to do with the definition presented for this olfactory family, as shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the yellow is the color of one of the main ingredients of this olfactory family: the vanilla ingredient. We can observe it in almost every perfume which has vanilla in its composition. They commonly have a liquid with a yellowish color, which influences the packaging when the bottle is transparent. This is, the liquid gives to the packaging a yellowish color².

Despite warm colors being the most mentioned in the oriental family, the colors white (seventeen mentions), and blue (thirteen mentions) were also regarded as representative. That is probably due to the reference these respondents may have from the Orient. Colors like blue and white are quite common in Asian landscapes. White and blue can be found in some packaging, however oriental fragrances usually have warm colors. It can be confirmed by checking the perfumes of the oriental family on the *Osmoz* magazine website. Lastly, regarding the colors mentioned for the attributes of *sophistication* and *sensuality*, we had the colors red and golden. These two colors are linked to the colors mentioned in the oriental family. However the third most mentioned color was purple/lilac, which is not as warm as red and yellow, but it is a color related to the royalty (Heller, 2013, p.196), and consequently with the idea of sophistication. It is not a warm color but it is also not a baseless choice, because we can find this kind of color in the packaging of oriental perfume from the *O Boticário* collection (Figure 7).

² In the website *Osmoz* (<http://www.osmoz.com>) we can find some examples of perfumes with vanilla. For instance we have *1881 en fleurs* (by Cerruti), *Aimez-moi* (by Caron), *Alchimie* (by Rochas), *Alien Essence Absolue* (by Thierry Mugler), and *Allure* (by Chanel).

CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

We live in an age where much of the attention, if not all, has converged on the consumer. One speaks about the power of influence of the consumers, the strength of collectiveness. One speaks of the importance of user experience, interactivity, and interface usability. It is worth highlighting that most of the time such experience begins at the point of sale, during the moment of the buying decision. The packaging in this sense plays an important role in the experience of the user/consumer. A packaging with inefficient visual communication runs the risk of being deprecated in the midst of competition. Packaging which does not appear in accordance with the content may generate frustration in the user. Moreover, in what concerns the packaging of perfumes, we argue that the more consonant with the perfume the visual communication is, the more successful the packaging will be. We assume that a visual language in synchrony with the smell will enhance the reception of the message you wish to convey.

In this paper we presented an investigation about the use of the colors to represent smells. From the results obtained through the survey we could conclude that consumers' associations between smells and colors are in consonance with what we can see in the market practice. We assume that it is a subject that requires thorough research. However, these initial results lead us to conclude that color perception can be linked to the olfactory perception. Even though each person has a particular perception, influenced by his own experience, social life also influences the way consumers perceive colors and smells. We believe that the better designers can understand the perception of consumers, the better and more efficiently they can design. As possibilities for future studies we point to the analysis of other visual elements such as shapes, typography, and textures. As well as research about the influence of colors over other fragrant products like shampoos, and air fresheners. In addition to this, we recommend other color perception surveys in which consumers are subjected to fragrance tests.

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